

TC FOR BE

TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE FOR BIODIVERSITY & EQUITY

Grant agreement number: 101082057

DELIVERABLE 1.1

Agrifood system modelling and scenarios for biodiversity

Lead party for deliverable: CIRAD
Document type: R
Due date of deliverable: 31-03-2024
Actual submission date: 29-07-2024
Version: 2.0
Dissemination level: Public
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Reviewers: Verina Ingram (WU)

WP	Task	Deliverable	Authors (lead and others)	Participant organisation	Dissemination level	Report Date & Version	Deliverable Delivery date (month)
1	1	D1.1	Rémi Prudhomme, Marie Ruille, Patrice Dumas, Pierre-Marie Aubert	CIRAD, IDDRI	Public	V 2.0	March

Partners

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Suggested citation: Rémi Prudhomme, Marie Ruillé, Patrice Dumas, Pierre-Marie Aubert (2024) Agrifood system modelling and scenarios for biodiversity TC4BE Deliverable 1.1. CIRAD and IDDRI. Wageningen University & Research, The Netherlands.

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This project is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101082057.

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Summary of Deliverable 1.1

Intent and method of the deliverable

The aim of this report is to present a **modelling framework** aimed at factoring in biodiversity thresholds on a global scale using a biomass-balance model of the world food system called BIODIVA. This framework relies on the identification of **six biodiversity proxies** and their associated thresholds, presented in a peer-reviewed paper (García-Vega et al. 2024): the total agricultural area, the pesticide pollution, the nitrogen (N) balance at a watershed level, share of semi natural vegetation in agricultural landscapes, cropping systems (intercropping and crop rotation), and management of grasslands. For each proxy, a computation method is proposed to identify the type of agricultural systems that would comply with each threshold. A systemic approach is then proposed to combine all proxies and identify the boundaries of a food system that would respect all thresholds. To reflect several proxies and their associated thresholds (N management, grassland management, semi natural vegetation and their implication for e.g. crop yields), BIODIVA combines three levels of spatial analysis: (i) a **fine scale at the grid point**, to consider certain surface and production constraints (the scale used here corresponds to a degree of resolution of 0.5x0.5, corresponding to the scale of the MAPSPAM data); (ii) a **watershed level**, which corresponds to an aggregation of the finer scale mentioned above for over 25,000 watersheds across the world; and (iii) an aggregation of **world regions** (large countries and aggregations of countries), for the following regions: Asia (excluding India and China), Brazil, China, Europe, Former Soviet Union, India, Latin America (excluding Brazil), Middle East and North Africa, and Sub-Saharan Africa.

Results

The first results obtained show that the level of N-constraint is extremely important. In several of the BIODIVA areas (China, the European Union, Middle East and Northern Africa), the available “space” for nitrogen application on cropland if we were to respect N thresholds would be negative, account being taken of other N sources (re-deposition, urban areas / sewage treatment, natural ecosystems). As such, it is the main determinant of total crop production in most regions considered in the model. Under the current simulation / set of assumptions, no more than 1/3 of the cereals needed to feed the expected 2050 world population a healthy diet could be produced.

Regarding animal production, things are more contrasted. Under the very ambitious assumption that all food waste and losses could be recycled and fed to monogastric animals (pork and poultry), monogastric meat production could exceed the demand. Ruminant production (milk and meat) would only meet respectively 60 and 40 % of demand.

Implications for project

More analysis is needed to identify if, and how, the N constraint can be partly lifted, and where. This will have critical implications to design a world food system that works for food security, biodiversity and climate. Scenario exercises at the landscape level to be carried out in WP5 will also benefit from these analysis. It is worth noting that BIODIVA cannot be downscaled to a landscape level and only aims to provide relevant results at a broad world region level.

Finally, the social / equity dimension has not yet been considered. This will be done in the future deliverable focusing on Europe and looking in particular at the cost of the transition.

Implications for policymakers /TC in agrifood systems

There are no implications for policy makers as the results presented here are still very preliminary.

Introduction

The intensification of agriculture has brought about unprecedented changes to agroecosystems, leading to significant biodiversity losses. As we strive to feed a growing global population, the need to explore sustainable agricultural practices becomes more urgent. This exploration seeks to balance food production with the conservation of biodiversity, ensuring that future generations can meet their nutritional needs without compromising the health of our planet's ecosystems.

Conventional agriculture often described in land-sparing strategy leads to a distant pollution of natural areas through pesticide drift in semi-natural vegetation of agricultural landscape, eutrophication of freshwater and ecosystem associated, acidification of distant ecosystem through redeposition of volatilised nitrogen used in agriculture... Inversely, biodiversity in agricultural landscapes plays a crucial role in maintaining ecosystem services, enhancing resilience against pests and diseases, and supporting the overall sustainability of agricultural systems. However, intensive farming practices have led to habitat loss, soil degradation, and a decline in species diversity. Explicitly representing biodiversity within agricultural landscapes is challenging due to the limitations of existing indicators such as the Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII) and the Mean Species Abundance (MSA).

This project aims to address these two challenges by investigating agricultural systems that are compatible with high levels of agro-biodiversity and assessing their impact on production levels. For this purpose, we will (i) define a safe agricultural space for biodiversity, (ii) implement this safe operating space to look at the food systems compatible with these environmental constraints. Defining a safe agricultural space for biodiversity consist in building a conceptual framework that uses agricultural practices that serve as proxies for biodiversity conservation, identifying thresholds and safe boundaries to ensure a high level of confidence that overall biodiversity is conserved. This step has been finished in the TC4BE project but is already published in the peer reviewed article. We consider that the article is in open access and do not need to be presented here.

In this report, we will rather focus on present the BiodivA model, which incorporates these safe boundaries for biodiversity into a framework allowing to link these biodiversity constraints with the agricultural and food system. In the second section, we aim to translate these safe boundaries into thresholds. Then in the third section, the impacts of these safe boundaries are translated into equations that quantify their effect on agricultural crop yield and animal production, including livestock density. The fourth section will present preliminary results obtained from the initial execution of the model, providing a foundation for further analysis and refinement. The implications for the TC4BE project, policymakers and stakeholders in agrofood systems are addressed in section 5.

This on-going work mobilize an important team effort in term of modelling which is difficult to see through this report. That's why we only present preliminary results. The modelling effort will continue with a sensitivity analysis of the main parameters of the model to better capture the uncertainty associated with these first results.

2.Method

2.1. Overview of the general method

The general method involves constructing a global scenario called **BiodivA** for the global food system that respects the biodiversity in agricultural and natural spaces. Based on an extensive review of the scientific literature (Garcia-Vega et al., 2024) (also a deliverable of this project) we defined agricultural and landscape management practices that ensure satisfactory levels of biodiversity in agricultural and natural areas.

The classification of these **agricultural boundaries for biodiversity** as described by Garcia-Vega et al. (2024) is first presented followed by the impacts of these constraints on plant and animal production. The model to assess the scenario is also called BiodivA. The model implements most of the scenario, but not all the constraints, and occasionally with simplifications.

2.2. Estimation of biodiversity boundaries

The figure below recalls the seven boundaries identified in the framework presented by Garcia-Vega et al (2024).

2.2.1. Agriculture area

In Garcia-Vega et al. (2024), authors suggest to keep agricultural lands outside the optimally-distributed 30% of protected natural areas, restricting total agricultural area to under 50% of the Earth's ice-free terrestrial surface, and contributing 20% of cropland and 100% of grasslands as other effective area-based conservation measures OECMs (Dudley et al. 2018).

In the model, cultivated areas follow Yu et al. (2020) distribution, which estimates land use in 2010 at 11.7 Mkm², representing 9% of the world's ice-free land area. Indeed, this is in the range of the literature review done by (Shaikh, Hadjikakou, and Bryan 2021) which estimates the cropland limits for the land-system change planetary boundary, adopting 10.6 Mkm² as the low estimate, 12.6 Mkm² as the best estimate, and 16.4 Mkm² as the high estimate of the global cropland limit. Using current repartition of agricultural areas is simple and avoids making specific assumptions. Other distributions could be relevant to improve the efficiency of wild biodiversity conservation; we leave that possibility open for future studies.

2.2.2. Pesticide pollution

As recommended by Garcia-Vega et al. (2024), the amount of pesticide used in our scenario is set at 50% of the EU's average pesticide input per hectare in 2021. Pesticides are uniformly applied in all countries to all crops. Note that pesticides are not represented explicitly in the model. The assumption behind the chosen approach is that the application level envisioned is a proxy for simultaneously (i) limit crop losses to pest; (ii) avoid impacts on biodiversity. As we shall see below, the N constraint appears much more

2.2.3. N atmospheric deposition

The main sources of NH₃ emissions are agricultural, accounting for over 75% of global ammonia emissions (Sapek, 2013). For simplicity's sake, other sources will be neglected here (food waste disposal, emissions from natural vegetation, biomass and fuel burning emission, etc).

In BiodivA, the critical threshold for deposition of N-NH₃ on natural vegetation is fixed at 3kgN. L⁻¹ of soil solution (Vries and Schulte-Uebbing, 2020):

$$\frac{Nvol_{C,bp} + Nvol_{fruits,bp} + Nvol_{veg,bp} + Nvol_{past,bp} + Nvol_{mono,bp}}{A_{bp}^{Tot}} = 3 \times \sum_i^{bp} soil.depth_i \times EAVSM_i$$

with $EAVSM_i$ which is the easily accessible volume of soil moisture, $soil.depth_i$ the soil depth at grid cell i (FAO and ISRIC 2012) and A_{bp}^{Tot} the total area of the pollution basin bp . The pollution basin is the surface unit over which the N pollution occurs.

- Nitrogen volatilization from fruits crops ($Nvol_{fruits,bp}$), vegetable crops ($Nvol_{veg,bp}$), pasture ($Nvol_{past,bp}$) and monogastric livestock system ($Nvol_{mono,bp}$) are not determined by N constraints (critical threshold) but are set according to production constraints.
- Nitrogen volatilization from cropland ($Nvol_{C,bp}$) is deduced from the critical threshold of deposition and the other sources of nitrogen volatilization:

$$Nvol_{C,bp} = 3 \times \sum_i^{bp} soil.depth_i \times EAVSM_i \times A_{bp}^{Tot} - Nvol_{fruits,bp} - Nvol_{veg,bp} - Nvol_{past,bp} - Nvol_{mono,bp}$$

2.2.4. N run-off

The critical threshold for N run-off is set at 2.5 mgN/L in freshwater (Liu et al., 2012; Garcia-Vega et al., 2024) and used to compute the compatible agricultural N use. First, the total N surplus summed over all grid cell in a basin is constrained by the amount of water at basin outlet ($W_{outlet,bp}$) multiplied by the N critical threshold. Second, the other sources of nitrogen run-off are deduced from the nitrogen limit to compute nitrogen left for crop cultivation. Other sources taken into

account in this study are (i) nitrogen run-off from pasture ($Nsurplus_{past,bp}$), (ii) nitrogen in waste water from urban areas ($Nsurplus_{urban,bp}$), (iii) the nitrogen run-off from natural areas ($Nsurplus_{natural,bp}$) and (iv) the nitrogen run-off from manure management ($Nsurplus_{man.mg,bp}$):

$$Nsurplus_{c,bp} + Nsurplus_{past,bp} + Nsurplus_{man.mg,bp} + Nsurplus_{urban,bp} + Nsurplus_{natural,bp} = 2.5 \times Woutlet_{bp}$$

- Nitrogen run-off from pasture ($Nsurplus_{past,bp}$) is deduced from the nitrogen balance estimated for natural pastures (see section 2.3.7).
- For the reference year (2010), nitrogen of waste water from urban areas ($Nsurplus_{urban,i}^{ref}$) is computed by allocating the global nitrogen surplus of human excretion around 2010 ($Nsurplus_{urban,world}$) (21TgN.year⁻¹) (Bodirsky et al. 2014), in grid cells based on the human consumption of protein. Agrimonde terra foresight healthy diet (Mora et al. 2020) is used for the human consumption of protein per capita ($n_i^{consumed/cap}$). The population (Pop_i) comes from population of the gridded population of the world. (CIESIN, 2016)

$$Nsurplus_{urban,i}^{ref} = \frac{Pop_i \times n_i^{consumed/cap}}{\sum_j^{world} Pop_j \times n_j^{consumed/cap}} \times Nsurplus_{urban,world}$$

The N surplus in the reference year is modified to take into account the water treatment infrastructure in 2050. Part of the nitrogen run-off is connected to the waste water treatment ($s_{connected,r}$) and treated to remove a part of the nitrogen ($s_{removal,r}$) (van Puijenbroek, Beusen, and Bouwman et al. (2019))

$$Nsurplus_{urban,i} = Nsurplus_{urban,i}^{ref} \left((1 - s_{connected,r}) + s_{connected,r} (1 - s_{removal,r}) \right)$$

The grid cell i is in r the region of the sewage treatment data.

- Nitrogen run-off from natural ecosystem ($Nsurplus_{natural,bp}$) is estimated at 0.5 mg/L of water run-off exiting from the cell ($Wrunoff_i$) (Vries and Schulte-Uebbing 2020). The water runoff comes from Yamazaki et al. (2011) The nitrogen run-off at the grid cell i is computed by allocating the water run-off to the natural areas ($A_{natural,i}$) based on their proportion in the grid cell, assuming a uniform runoff among different land uses:

$$Nsurplus_{natural,i} = 0.5 \times \frac{A_{natural,i}}{A_{c,i} + A_{natural,i} + A_{past,i} + A_{urban,i}} \times Wrunoff_i$$

With $A_{c,i}$ the total area of cropland, $A_{urban,i}$ the total urban areas and $A_{past,i}$ the total area of pasture.

2.2.5. Within-fields semi-natural habitats

To keep a minimum of within-field semi-natural habitat in the BiodivA scenario, at least 20 % of the landscape per 1sq.km grid cell is allocated to natural habitats or extensive pastures (Garcia-Vega et al., 2024). The integrity index defined by Declerck et al. (2021) is used to compute the share of the agricultural landscape with semi-natural vegetation in a 1 km buffer. Then, at a grid of 10km squared resolution the average in each grid of this integrity score is computed. For grids with an integrity score below the critical threshold of 20 %, a part of the grid previously in cropland is allocated to natural areas as follows:

$$A_{c,i} = A_{c,i}^{2010} - \max(0, 0.2 - EI_i^{2010}) \times \frac{A_{c,i}^{2010}}{A_{c,i}^{2010} + A_{urban,i}^{2010}} \times A_{c,i}^{2010}$$

With $A_{c,i}^{2010}$ which is the total area of cropland at the grid cell i for the 2010 reference year, $A_{urban,i}^{2010}$ which is the total urban area at the grid cell i for the 2010 reference year and EI_i^{2010} which is the ecosystem integrity defined by (DeClerck et al. 2021) as:

$$EI_i^{2010} = 1 - \frac{A_{C,i}^{2010} + A_{Urban,i}^{2010}}{A_i^{2010}}$$

With A_i^{2010} total area including bare soil but not water bodies, snow and ice areas (Lamarche et al. 2017).

2.2.6. Intercropping

In the BiodivA scenario, promoting crop diversity is achieved in particular through intercropping. Here, intercropping is defined as the cultivation of at least two crops in the same place for at least part of their growth cycle, which means that relay cropping is also considered as intercropping. Intercropping is only considered between cereals (C3 cereals and maize) and legumes because this is the most common and most studied association, and according to some authors would be the most performing (Jensen et al., 2020; Martin-Guay et al., 2018). The area of cereals and legumes in association is maximized at the grid cell level.

2.2.7. Crop rotations

As in Garcia-Vega et al. (2024), we considered that fruits and vegetables are cultivated in multi-specific systems. We also assume that the harvested areas are directly determined by the demand. The surface area of fruit and vegetable crops ($A_{fruit,i}$, $A_{veg,i}$) is therefore set as a function of a target demand level ($D_{fruits.veg.world}^{diet}$) and the surface area of fruit and vegetables in the 2010 reference year ($A_{fruit,i}^{2010}$, $A_{veg,i}^{2010}$):

$$A_{fruit,i} = \frac{D_{fruits.veg.world}^{diet}}{D_{fruits.veg.world}^{2010}} \times A_{fruit,i}^{2010}$$

$$A_{veg,i} = \frac{D_{fruits.veg.world}^{diet}}{D_{fruits.veg.world}^{2010}} \times A_{veg,i}^{2010}$$

As mentioned by Garcia-Vega et al. (2024) “there is no level of complexity for crop rotation identified as optimal for biodiversity”, crop rotations in BiodivA are fixed to an organic one described in the literature (Barbieri et al., 2017). Barbieri et al. (2017) characterize the typical crop rotation in organic farming worldwide as lasting around 4.5 years with a variation of approximately 1.7 years compared to conventional agriculture. These rotations typically consist of four distinct crop categories, prioritizing temporary fodder, pulses, and secondary cereals over primary cereals when compared to conventional rotations.

In BiodivA, this implies that due to organic crop rotations, cultivated areas for each crop c at the grid cell i $Aorg_{c,i}$ should either increase or decrease compared to the 2010 reference year as follows:

- For crops with reducing areas:

$$Aorg_{c,i} = aorg_{CT,r}^{2010} \times A_{c,i}^{2010} \times \frac{A_{c,i}^{2010} - A_{fruit,i} - A_{veg,i}}{A_{c,i}^{2010}}$$

With $aorg_{CT,r}^{2010}$ the organic-to-conventional ratio of timeshare in rotation for the crop category CT of crop c in region r (based on timeshares in Table S2 of (Barbieri et al. 2017)), $A_{c,i}^{2010}$ the total area of cropland at the grid cell i for the 2010 reference year and $A_{c,i}^{2010}$ the cultivated area of the crop c for the 2010 reference year.

- For crops with increasing areas:

$$Aorg_{c,i} = por_{CT,r}^{2010} \times \left(A_{c,i}^{2010} - A_{fruit,i} - A_{veg,i} - \sum_u^{decreasing\ crops} Aorg_{u,i} \right)$$

With $por_{CT,r}^{2010} = \frac{aorg_{CT,r}^{2010} \times A_{c,i}^{2010}}{\sum_j^{increas} aorg_{CT,r}^{2010} \times A_{c,j}^{2010}}$ the coefficient that redistribute freed land.

2.2.8. Grassland management

In BiodivA scenario, we assumed that pastures areas remain the same as in the 2010 reference year at the grid cell i :

$$A_{past,i} = A_{past,i}^{2010}$$

Also, pastures are not fertilized and the livestock density of ruminants per hectare is set in order to use 70 % of aboveground grass biomass used as their feed.

2.3. Geographical scale of aggregation

In the model, three geographical levels can be considered:

- Aggregations of **countries in world regions** (one or more aggregated countries), with the following regions used in the default case: Asia (excluding India and China), Brazil, China, Europe, Former Soviet Union, India, Latin America (excluding Brazil), Middle East and North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa.
- A **fine scale at the grid point**, to consider certain surface and production constraints. The scale used here corresponds to a degree of resolution of 0.5x0.5, corresponding to the scale of the MAPSPAM data.
- **Areas**, which correspond to an aggregation of the finer scale mentioned above. In practice, these aggregated surfaces correspond to pollution basins (see section 2.2.3 and 2.2.4).

2.4. Plant production sector

In BiodivA, yield formation is represented as a potential yield with modifying factors, for most crops. The yield is noted ($Y_{c,i}$). The potential yield and nitrogen availability are included in the ($f_N^i(n_{source,c}^i)$) term. Other yield factors are also represented based on pesticide use ($rpest_{country,c}$), the presence of semi-natural vegetation ($rSNV_{i,c}$), and the presence of associated crops ($rIC_{country,c}$) using the constraints and practices defined in sections 2.2.2, 2.2.5 and 2.2.6 respectively.

$$Y_{c,i} = f_N^i(n_{source,c}^i) \times rpest_{country,c} \times rSNV_{i,c} \times rIC_{country,c}$$

Vegetables, fruits and legumes, do not respond to nitrogen in the same ways than other crops. The literature on organic agriculture do not describe yield reductions for fruits and vegetables (Seufert, Ramankutty, and Foley 2012) because the yield reduction corresponding to pests appears to be fully compensated by agroecological practices. The same assumption is made for legumes, because no studies were found on the effect of pests on yield reduction in organic agriculture. Therefore, the yield of vegetable, fruits and legumes is represented differently.

The yield of vegetable, fruits or legumes ($Y_{Veg/Fruits/Leg,i}$) is computed more simply by using the potential yield ($Y_{pot_{Veg/Fruits/Leg,i}}$) and applying an average global yield index ($YI_{Veg/Fruits/Leg,i}^{2010,first\ decile}$) determined on 2010 data and applied all over the world. The first decile is used for the yield index in the BiodivA scenario.

$$Y_{Veg/Fruits/Leg,i} = YI_{Veg/Fruits/Leg,i}^{2010,first\ decile} \times Y_{pot_{Veg/Fruits/Leg,i}}$$

2.4.1. Yield response to nitrogen for field crops

The following non-linear yield response function (Y_c^r) to nitrogen ($n_{S,c}^r$) is used:

$$Y_c^r(n_{S,c}^r) = Y_{max_{c,r}} \times \left(1 - e^{-t \times n_{S,c}^r}\right)$$

With $Y_{max_{c,r}}$ maximal yield of crop c in the region r , obtained from the reference year data, and $n_{S,c}^r$ the total nitrogen inputs from synthetic and organic fertilization, deposition and biological nitrogen fixation.

2.4.2. Effect of pesticide level on yield

The yield gap due to a 50% reduction in pesticides used in Europe by 2021 is set here at -10%. Some

authors have found a different yield gap between organic (zero conventional pesticides) and conventional farming for the same level of nitrogen: -30% for Seufert et al. (2012) and -9% for Ponisio et al. (2015). We used 20% for the zero-pesticide yield gap ($apest$) and interpolate linearly. The assumption of a reduction of yield of 10% for a reduction of 50% of pesticides application is more optimistic than the result of Hossard et al. (2014), which found a yield reduction of 20% for halving pesticide use for wheat in Europe.

For the yield gap (ratio between potential and realized yield) due to pesticide level use, we assume that the relative effect of pesticides on yield is the same in Europe as in the rest of the world:

$$r_{pest_c} = \min\left(0.9, a_{pest} * \frac{pest}{UE.2021} + (0.9 - a_{pest})\right)$$

With $pest$ the total pesticide use at national scale defined by FAOSTAT (2015), uniformly allocated between crops and area, $EU.2021$ the pesticide use of European Union in 2021, considered to be associated with a yield gap of 0.9. We set the maximum yield gap attainable despite pests at 0.9, which is a reasonable value for developed countries. According to the literature, there are more pests in tropical regions due to higher plant diversity (Liebold et al., 2018). The assumption of homogenous effect all over the world may therefore need to be modified with data on the relative effect of pesticide use in such contexts (Civitello et al., 2015).

2.4.3. Effect of pollination on yield

We set a minimum of 20%.km² of croplands as semi-natural vegetation (see section 2.2.5). The integration of semi-natural habitats into cultivated land can therefore help to increase yields through an increase in regulating ecosystem services. The effect of pollination on yield is modelled as:

$$rSNV_c = 1 + \frac{apoll}{1-apoll} \times \frac{1}{1-e^{-a \times 0.2}} \times (1 - e^{-a \times SNV_c^{gc}})$$

The production benefit due to pollination is dependent to the crop dependency to pollinator of each crop and the share of natural habitat in agriculture landscape (SNV_c^{gc}). $apoll$ is the yield deficit (0,5,25,65,95%) representing the crop dependency to pollinators found in SNV, based on Aizen et al. (2009). If $apoll = 0$, the crop is not dependant to pollinators and there will be no yield losses. For SNV of 0.2, the full effect of dependency on pollination is achieved:

$$rSNV_c(0.2) = \frac{1}{1 - apoll}$$

2.4.4. Effect of intercropping on yield

In BiodivA, the maximum possible intercropping area per grid cell is realized (see section 2.2.6) which means for each grid point i the total area in intercropping ($Aic_{leg.cereals,i}^{2010}$) is limited by the smallest area between the area of legume ($A_{leg,i}$) and cereal crops ($A_{p.cereals,i} + A_{s.cereals,i}$). The areas are set according to SPAM data for year 2010, the reference year for the model here, modified by the hypotheses on rotations (section 2.2.7).

$$Aic_{leg.cereals,i}^{2010} = \min\left(\sum_c^{legumes} A_{c,i}, \sum_c^{cereals} A_{c,i}\right)$$

We assumed here that the effect of intercropping on yield (rIC_c) decreases linearly as a function of the amount of nitrogen inputs ($n_{S,c}^i$) and was deduced from the average effect of intercropping on Land Equivalent Ratio (LER) of the meta-analysis by Li et al. (2020). We use a simple linear relation based on the data of "other crops" of the figure 6.a from Li et al. (2020). We assume that the high N inputs is 100 kg/ha for LER 1.1 and low N inputs is 10 kg/ha for LER 1.19, leading to a slope of 0.001 per unit of applied nitrogen per unit of areas for the effect of nitrogen application on the LER.

The overall effect of intercropping (rIC_c) is weighted by the share of crop intercropped ($sIC_{i,c}$), leading to:

$$rIC_c = (1.2 - 0.001 \times n_{S,c}^i) * sIC_{i,c} + (1 - sIC_{i,c})$$

$$\text{With } sIC_{i,c} = \frac{A_{i,c}^{2010} \times A_{leg.cereals,i}^{2010}}{A_{C,i}^{2010} - A_{fruit,i}^{2010} - A_{veg,i}^{2010}}$$

2.4.5. Constraints on N from pollution

In BiodivA, the nitrogen balance is constrained by the level of nitrogen lixiviation in water run-off and the nitrogen deposition compatible with high biodiversity level and other sources of nitrogen run-off and volatilisation outside the plant sector (see section 2.3 and 2.4). The allocation between crops and grids inside the pollution basin could be based on multiple criteria (equal allocation of N surpluses, efficiency allocation, self-sufficiency allocation...). Here, to compute the N surplus rate of the crop c in the grid cell, N surplus of all crops at the pollution basin levels are allocated based on an equal allocation of N surpluses among crops. Therefore, N lixiviation and N volatilization for each crop at the location i $nlixiv_{i,c}$ and $nvol_{i,c}$ respectively, result from the allocation of the nitrogen left for cropland in the pollution basin due to lixiviation constraint ($Nsurplus_{C,bp}$) and volatilisation constraint ($N_{vol,bp}^C$).

$$nlixiv_{i,c}^{BiodivA} = \frac{A_{i,c}^{2010}}{A_{C,bp}^{2010}} \times Nsurplus_{C,bp}^{BiodivA} \times \frac{1}{A_{i,c}^{BiodivA}}$$

$$nvol_{i,c}^{BiodivA} = \frac{A_{i,c}^{2010}}{A_{C,bp}^{2010}} \times Nvol_{C,bp}^{BiodivA} \times \frac{1}{A_{i,c}^{BiodivA}}$$

With $A_{i,c}^{2010}$, $A_{C,bp}^{2010}$, $A_{i,c}^{BiodivA}$ the harvested area of the crop in the grid cell i, the harvested area of all crops in the pollution basin and the harvested area of the crop c with the BiodivA scenario, respectively.

This constraint allows us to fix the maximum nitrogen input which can be applied on crops:

$$n_{S,c}^i = \alpha_{N,c}^{global} \times f_c^{BiodivA}(n_{S,c}^i) + nlixiv_{i,c} + nvol_{i,c}$$

With $f_c^{BiodivA}$ the yield response function to nitrogen, $\alpha_{N,c}^{global}$ which is the nitrogen content of above ground biomass and $n_{S,c}^i$ the total nitrogen inputs.

The synthetic nitrogen rate ($nsynth_{i,c}^{BiodivA}$) is deduced from this nitrogen source for each grid cell and each crop ($n_{S,c}^i$) by subtracting from this total source of nitrogen the other sources of nitrogen that are necessarily applied due to other constraints. Nitrogen deposition rate ($ndep_{i,c}$) occurs naturally. The nitrogen recovered from the previous rotation by the cereals comes from the nitrogen left by the legumes ($nrot_{i,c}$). In the BiodivA scenario, the manure applied ($nman.applied_{i,c}$) is equal to the manure collected from monogastric production, and equal to 50% of the manure collected from ruminants uniformly applied on cropland. Finally, biological nitrogen fixation occurs for legumes c ($nBNF_{i,c}$).

$$nsynth_{i,c}^{BiodivA} = n_{S,c}^i - ndep_{i,c} - nrot_{i,c} - nman.applied_{i,c} - nBNF_{i,c}$$

2.5. Animal production sector

The animal production sector is divided into two major categories: monogastrics and ruminants, whose products are presented in the table 1.

Table 1 Animal systems and their production

	Animal system	Production
Ruminant	Beef cattle	Meat
	Bovine diary	Milk including butter

	Sheep and goats meat	Meat
	Sheep and goat dairy	Milk including butter
Monogastrics	Pigs	Pigmeat
	Poultry	Poultry meat, eggs

In the model, livestock density is defined by the amount of human waste for monogastrics and the grass resource for ruminants. Human food and livestock feed do not directly compete with each other.

2.5.1. Monogastric animals

Monogastric livestock systems are based on the systems presented by van Hal et al. (2019), with pigs for meat production and poultry for both meat and egg production (broiler chicken and laying hen system in van Hal et al. (2019), respectively). Production and feed requirements are determined using coefficients provided by the same authors, based on the “optimal conversion from low-opportunity-cost feedstuff to animal source food” case.

Livestock density is defined by the amount of food waste available, which in turn is calculated using the waste fractions of Gustavsson et al. (2011). We determine post-transformation digestible energy available as waste by subtracting consumption energy from available energy. We assume that 100% of the digestible energy in waste is available as feed for monogastrics. Currently, in countries with a high level of food losses given to monogastrics, the share of waste quantities is 47% in the country with the highest share, Japan (Saleemdeen et al., 2017). Food energy waste allocation between animals (i.e. pigs and poultry) is based on current demand in each given region.

Total energy in feed is obtained by using van Hal et al. (2019) feed categories shares (Figure 3) together with metabolizable energy content from feedipedia (Heuzé et al., 2013)). For byproducts, the products from van Hal et al. (2019) appendix are mapped to feedipedia products, for wastes a selection of product typical of wastes in feedipedia is used. The average metabolizable energy obtained for waste of 12 MJ/kg is well within the range of metabolizable energy found in van Hal et al. (2019) appendix by country. The share in energy content of waste over total energy content applied to food waste determines the total input feed energy by monogastric animal category and by country.

The production of monogastric products is computed as total feed energy divided by feed requirements coefficients. The feed requirement coefficients are based on an update of Herrero et al. (2013) to the year 2011, at the regional level. The number of heads and amount of nitrogen excreted and applied ($nman.applied_{i,c}$) are based on the coefficients of Herrero et al. (2013). However, only the coefficients of the best countries (with the higher efficiency) are retained and applied to each country in a world region.

In the model, the geographical distribution of monogastric animals is defined according to the Gridded Livestock of the World (GLW) developed by the FAO.

2.5.2. Ruminant animals

➤ Livestock system assumptions

Ruminant livestock systems are assumed to be homogeneous at the global scale, i.e., animal management is similar everywhere, based on efficient management targeting production. Feed is mainly grass-based, supplemented by crop co-products. Livestock density depends on the amount of grass in the pasture. In the BiodivA scenario, temporary pastures are managed in the same way as permanent pastures. They are managed without fertilization, and it is assumed that the pasture is 15% leguminous. In temperate zones, this proportion is obtained without sowing after 5 years

without fertilization (Vazquez et al., 2022). In tropical conditions, this may require planting leguminous shrubs (Murgueitio et al., 2011).

To define the characteristics (i.e., coefficient) of the animals in each ruminant system (Beef cattle, Bovine dairy, Sheep and goats meet and Sheep and goats dairy), we use systems from European “model countries” with good plant-to-animal energy conversion efficiency and a high proportion of grass in the feed intake: Ireland, Slovenia, Belgium and Albania for the Beef cattle, Bovine dairy, meat sheep and goats and Sheep and goats dairy systems respectively.

➤ Nitrogen balance in grassland- based ruminant systems

The N sources for extensive pasture includes nitrogen deposition ($N_{dep,grass}^{country}$), nitrogen left from the previous rotation through residues ($N_{rotation}^{grid}$), biological fixation nitrogen ($N_{BNF}^{country}$), and nitrogen excreted on the pasture by the animal “anim” in the system “syst” ($N_{excreted}^{anim,syst,grid}$). These sources are balanced by the nitrogen outputs: nitrogen grazed or harvested for animal ($N_{harvested}^{grid}$), nitrogen left for the next rotation through residues (N_{left}^{grid}) and nitrogen lost by lixiviation (N_{leach}^{grid}) and by volatilisation (N_{vol}^{grid}).

$$\begin{aligned} & N_{excreted}^{anim,syst,grid} + N_{BNF}^{grid} + N_{dep,grass}^{country} + N_{rotation}^{grid} + N_{manure}^{grid} \\ &= N_{harvested}^{grid} + N_{left}^{grid} + N_{leach}^{grid} + N_{vol}^{grid} + \Delta N_{soil}^{grid} \end{aligned}$$

The variation of N in soil (ΔN_{soil}^{grid}) is null because we consider that the nitrogen is balanced for sustainability consideration. The two side of the equation are linked by balances done at the excretion stage, by residues and at the plant absorption stage. At the excretion stage, part of the nitrogen excreted ($n_{excreted}^{anim,syst,grid}$) can be collected and stored in a manure management system ($FRAC_{collected}^{world}$), lost through leaching or volatilization ($FRAC_{leach}^{world}$ and $FRAC_{vol}^{world}$ defined in Table 10.22 of IPCC refinement guideline (2019) and depend on the livestock density of the pasture for each animal “anim” in the ruminant system “syst” ($density_{pasture}^{anim,syst,grid}$).

$$\begin{aligned} N_{PRP}^{anim,syst,grid} &= (1 - FRAC_{collected}^{world}) \times (1 - FRAC_{leach}^{world} - FRAC_{vol}^{world}) \times density_{pasture}^{anim,syst,grid} \times n_{excr}^{anim,syst,grid} \\ N_{leach}^{grid} &= FRAC_{leach}^{world} \times density_{pasture}^{anim,syst,grid} \times n_{excr}^{anim,syst,grid} \\ N_{vol}^{grid} &= FRAC_{vol}^{world} \times density_{pasture}^{anim,syst,grid} \times n_{excr}^{anim,syst,grid} \end{aligned}$$

For residues, a share of the aboveground biomass is not harvested and forms residues ($\alpha_{residues,harv}^{grid}$) which are themselves for a part lost through leaching ($FRAC_{residues,leach}^{world}$) and for a part left for the next rotation based on a part of the equation 11.6 of (Ogle et al. 2019):

$$\begin{aligned} N_{left}^{grid} &= (1 - \alpha_{utilisation}^{grid}) \times (s_{legumes,grass}^{world} \times NPP_{AGbiomass}^{grid} \times \alpha_{leg/grass}^{grid} \times \alpha_{N,leg}^{grid} + (1 - s_{legumes,grass}^{world}) \times \frac{N_{harvested,grass}^{grid}}{\alpha_{utilisation}^{grid}}) \\ N_{rotation}^{grid} &= (1 - FRAC_{residues,leach}^{world}) \times N_{left}^{grid} \end{aligned}$$

With $\alpha_{N,residues}^{grid}$ and $\alpha_{N,grass}^{grid}$ the nitrogen content of residues and grass respectively.

At the plant absorption stage, we distinguish the legumes representing a share of the pasture ($s_{legumes,grass}^{world}$) and the grass. For simplicity, we assume that all the nitrogen excreted, deposited and left in the previous rotation is used by grass and for a percent of legume corresponding to the nitrogen not biologically fixed (α_{Ndfa}^{world}). The nitrogen harvested from legumes is:

$$N_{harvested,leg}^{grid} = \alpha_{utilisation}^{grid} \times NPP_{AGbiomass}^{grid} \times \alpha_{leg/grass}^{grid} \times \alpha_{N,leg}^{grid}$$

D1.1 Agrifood system modelling and scenario for biodiversity

With $\alpha_{leg/grass}^{grid}$ the ratio of legume yield divided by the NPP of aboveground biomass in the grid cell, $n_{fix\ per\ DM,grass}^{world}$ the nitrogen fixation per unit of biomass, $\alpha_{N,leg}^{grid}$ the nitrogen content of legume, α_{Ndfa}^{world} the share of nitrogen in the legume coming from BNF, and $NPP_{AGbiomass}^{grid}$ the net primary productivity of aboveground biomass in grassland biomes.

The nitrogen balance of grass and the legume nitrogen that is not fixed is:

$$N_{PRP}^{anim,syst,grid} + N_{rotation}^{grid} + N_{dep,grass}^{country} = \frac{N_{harvested,grass}^{grid}}{\alpha_{utilisation}^{grid}} + \frac{N_{harvested,leg}^{grid} \times (1 - \alpha_{Ndfa}^{world})}{\alpha_{utilisation}^{grid}} + N_{left}^{grid}$$

With $\alpha_{utilisation}^{grid}$ the share of aboveground biomass harvested. $N_{harvested,grass}^{grid}$ is solved from the balance.

The nitrogen harvest results from the weighted average of legume and grass harvested nitrogen (respectively $N_{harvested,grass}^{grid}$ and $N_{harvested,leg}^{grid}$) based on their relative share in the mixture (respectively $s_{legumes,grass}^{world}$ and $1 - s_{legumes,grass}^{world}$):

$$N_{harvested}^{grid} = (1 - s_{legumes,grass}^{world}) \times N_{harvested,grass}^{grid} + s_{legumes,grass}^{world} \times N_{harvested,leg}^{grid}$$

2.6. Calibration of the BiodivA model

The key parameters which are calibrated are the parameters of the plant yield response function and those of the pasture nitrogen balance.

2.6.1. Plant yield response function

We calibrate the current yield response function to nitrogen by estimating the coefficient t (see section 2.4.1) at the global level using country scale FAOSTAT data (FAOSTAT 2015) for yields, the national nitrogen balance of Zhang et al. (2015) and potential yield are computed using the yield gap from the crop model LPJmL (Bondeau et al. 2007) on the actual yield ($Y_{N,c}^r$) maps provided by the SPAM dataset. Table 2 shows the 42 SPAM crops included in this dataset and their respective FAO classification. We remove to this global dataset countries with nitrogen input below 18 kgN.ha⁻¹ and countries with a yield index above one which do not provide relevant information to estimate the yield response function to nitrogen. The yield response function to nitrogen is then estimated by crop type by fitting the yield index with the total nitrogen input with a quantile regression for the highest decile (Fig.1).

The spatial heterogeneity of yield due to different local crop mixes inside our crop types (for example banana and salad in fruits and vegetables) is included in the local potential yield which is the weighted average of the 42 SPAM crop described in Yu et al. (2020), which is depends on the pedoclimatic conditions and the phenology of each SPAM plant.

To validate our yield response function, we compute the total input nitrogen ($N_{S,c}^{global}$, called hereafter the maximum nitrogen input) needed to reach the potential yield ($Y_c^{r,max}$):

$$N_{S,c}^{global} = \frac{1}{t_c^{global}} \times \log \left(1 - \frac{Y_{N,c}^r}{Y_c^{r,max}} \right)$$

The maximum nitrogen input is then compared with the literature (Table 3). In case of difference with literature, we change the selection of countries included in the quantile regression by increasing the minimum nitrogen input and by decreasing the maximum YI index necessary to be included in the data used to fit the regression.

The final yield response function to all input is:

$$Y_{c,i} = f_N^i(n_{source,c}^i) \times r_{pest,country,c} \left(\frac{pest^{EU}}{2} \right) \times rSNV_{i,c}(0.2) \times rIC_{country,c}(N_{S,c}^r)$$

Crop SPAM	FAO Classification
Arabica coffee	Stimulates
Banana	Fruits
Barley	Cereals
Bean	Pulses
Cassava	Roots & Tuber
Chickpea	Pulses
Cocoa	Stimulates
Coconut	Oilcrops
Cotton	Fibres
Cowpea	Pulses
Groundnut	Oilcrops
Lentil	Pulses
Maize	Cereals
Oilpalm	Oilcrops
Other Cereals	Cereals
Other Fibre	Fibres
Other oil crop	Oilcrops
Other pulses	Pulses
Other roots	Roots & Tuber
Pearl millet	Cereal
Pigeon pea	Pulses
Plantain	Fruits
Potato	Root & Tuber
Rapeseed	Oilcrops
Rest of crops	-
Rice	Cereals
Robusta coffee	Stimulates
Sesame seed	Oilcrops
Small millet	Cereals
Sorghum	Cereals
Soybean	Oilcrops
Sugar cane	Sugar crops
Sugarbeet	Sugar crops
Sunflower	Oilcrops
Sweet potato	Root & Tuber
Tea	Stimulates
Temperate fruit	Fruits
Tobacco	Stimulates
Tropical fruit	Fruits
Vegetables	Vegetables
Wheat	Cereals
Yams	Root & Tuber

Table 2 Crop SPAM and their FAO classification

Figure 1 Quantile regression using an exponential curve shape on the highest deciles (▲) to estimate the response function of yield to nitrogen for most of the crop.

Tableau 3 Comparison between the Nitrogen input to maximize yield found in the literature and that simulated by the model

	Nitrogen input for maximum yield in literature	Nitrogen input for maximum yield in this study (kg N ha ⁻¹)
Maize	325 to 497 kg ha ⁻¹ (Huang et al. 2021), 360 kg N ha ⁻¹ (Gao et al. 2020) in China	400
Wheat	250 and 337 kg N ha ⁻¹ (Ma et al. 2019) or 226 and 342 kg ha ⁻¹ (Z. Li et al. 2020) in China	245
Rice	150 kg/ha in Senegal (Djaman et al. 2018), 150-200 kg ha ⁻¹ (Cao et al. 2023), 179.0–214.9 kg N ha ⁻¹ (Ding et al. 2021) in China	210
Other cereals	147 kg N ha ⁻¹ in Idaho (Rogers et al. 2022), 230 kg N ha ⁻¹ in Ethiopia	155
Rapeseed	180-230 kg ha ⁻¹ in Poland (Groth, Sokólski, and Jankowski 2020)	347
Sunflowerseed	90-120 kg ha ⁻¹ in Brazil (Coêlho et al. 2022)	220
Oilpalm	260 kg ha ⁻¹ in (Woittiez et al. 2017)	150
Roots and tuber	300kg/ha ⁻¹ for potato in various countries (Milroy, Wang, and Sadras 2019), 300 kg/ha for potato in Turkish (Akkamis and Caliskan 2023)	200
Sugar plants	No references found	255
Fibers	No references found	235

For crops categories “Pulses”, “Soyabeans”, “Vegetables” and “Fruits”, which are not responding to nitrogen in the same way than other crops (see section 2.4.), an average yield index is fixed respectively at 0.71, 0.47 and 0.65 using a decile regression on the 10 % percent highest decile (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Linear and quantile regression between actual yields and potential yields to estimate the average yield index used in the BiodivA scenario for crop categories "fruits," "vegetables," "pulses" and "soyabeans"

2.6.2. Pasture nitrogen balance

We use the ORCHIDEE land surface model grassland aboveground NPP per grid cell. Several parameters related to the nitrogen balance of pastures (see section 2.5.2) are calibrated based on existing literature. The nitrogen content of legume ($\alpha_{N,leg}^{grid}$) and the nitrogen fixation per unit of biomass ($n_{fix\ per\ FM,grass}^{world}$) are set at 2.6% and 0.018 kgN/kgFM based on Vazquez et al. (2022).

The share of nitrogen in the legume coming from biological nitrogen fixation (BNF) is deduced from $n_{fix\ per\ FM,grass}^{world}$ from Vazquez et al. (2022):

$$\alpha_{Ndfa}^{world} = \frac{n_{fix\ per\ FM,grass}^{world}}{\alpha_{N,leg}^{grid}} = \frac{0.018}{0.026} = 0.69$$

The share of legumes in the pasture ($s_{legumes,grass}^{world}$) is set at 0.15 based on Vazquez et al. (2022). The share of NPP harvested ($\alpha_{utilisation}^{grid}$) is set at 0.7 per deduction to $\alpha_{residues,harv}^{grid}$ because we assumed that 30% of the total biomass is not harvested and therefore constitutes residues.

The parameter $\alpha_{leg/grass}^{grid}$ (i.e., ratio of legume yield divided by the NPP in the grid cell) is set by comparing ORCHIDEE values in the humid tropic and the equatorial area with tropical legumes maximum yields found in the literature. We retain for ORCHIDEE 25 tDM/hectare, the values in the humid tropic and the equatorial areas being in the 20 to 30 tonnesDM/hectare range. In Thomas 1995, nitrogen fixed, Ndfa and nitrogen content leads to 7 to 10 tonnesDM/hectare. Hauser et al. 2002 maximum value is at 8.8 tonnes/hectare. Tenakwa et al (2021) first cut plus regrowth yield is 9 tonnes/hectare. Based on this literature we consider that 8 tonnesDM/hectare is a good estimation, which leads to 0.3 for $\alpha_{leg/grass}^{grid}$.

Figure 3 Livestock density of ruminants (Total livestock units/ha)

Then, livestock density of ruminant (Figure 3), pasture yield index, pasture NUE ($=\frac{N_{\text{harvested}}+N_{\text{left}}}{N_{\text{input}}}$), grass yield (only harvested aboveground biomass) and legumes yield (only harvested aboveground biomass) simulated with the BiodivA scenario are checked after parameters calibration of nitrogen balance of pasture (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Pasture NUE (a), Pasture yield index (b), Grass yield and legumes yield simulated after parameters calibration of nitrogen balance of pasture with the BiodivA scenario.

Pasture nitrogen efficiency (NUE) is very high in all regions of the globe, with an average NUE of around 0.7. Moreover, grass yields are highest in northern South America, with maximum values of 12 Mg/ha. The highest legume yields are found mainly in northern South America, Sub-Saharan Africa and Southeast Asia, with yields of over 5 Mg/ha (Figure 4). These values are consistent with those found at these latitudes. It is also at these latitudes that ruminant density is highest, given that ruminant feed is almost entirely grass (Figure 3) (see section 2.5.2).

3. First results

In the following, we will present results on the nitrogen constraint which appear to be the most constraining boundary for the agricultural and food system globally. Then we will present the food production compatible with these boundaries in comparison with the demand for the corresponding food product to translate how constraining are the biodiversity boundaries on the food system.

3.1. Nitrogen constraints on cropland

Initially, the maximum quantity of nitrogen ("N limit") that can be applied to cropland was calculated for each large region (Figure 5). Other nitrogen sources (manure management, natural areas, pasture, and urban areas) apart from crop production were also calculated ("N losses"). The difference between "N limit" and "N losses", "N balance," is the theoretical amount of nitrogen that could be applied to cropland surfaces.

We observe that regions with a high pollution capacity correspond not only to areas with high rainfall, primarily around equatorial zones, but also to those where watersheds are the largest. For example, in the Middle East and North Africa, the nitrogen balance ("N balance") is negative (-1×10^9 Mg). Indeed, solely with nitrogen from urban areas, critical N limits are already exceeded. This is explained by the fact that this region is situated in arid zones with a high population density where water is located. This means that for this type of region, respecting the threshold on eutrophication requires a decrease of non-agricultural sectors N leaching. In fact, even with organic agriculture (without synthetic fertilization), other nitrogen sources already exceed critical limits.

Other countries like India also have a negative nitrogen balance (-0.5×10^9 Mg) or are close to critical N limits like China. These are regions where nitrogen quantities from urban areas are also very high, as well as those from pastures for China. This can be justified by a significant presence of pastures across the Chinese territory.

Figure 5 Nitrogen pollution limit and nitrogen loss balance

For certain regions like Brazil, Latin America, Canada, and the European Union, the nitrogen balance is positive, indicating that it is still possible to apply nitrogen to cropland areas. However, the "N balance" represents the theoretical quantity, whereas "N for cropland" is the amount actually applicable. This means that the N balance can be above or below the quantity of nitrogen that could actually be applied to cropland areas. "N for cropland" is reasoned at the watershed scale rather than at the regional scale like the "N balance". For example, in the Former Soviet Union, the nitrogen balance is positive, so theoretically there would be space to apply synthetic nitrogen to cropland areas. But in reality, it is a region with limited cultivated areas, so the nitrogen that can be applied to cropland areas is much lower. Conversely, where the "N balance" was negative, such as in India, it is still possible to apply nitrogen in these regions. Indeed, certain watersheds in India exceed critical thresholds while some nearby watersheds can still receive nitrogen. This underscores the importance of reasoning at the watershed scale rather than at the region scale, as "the space for pollution in the region" may be overestimated.

3.2. Nitrogen supply for cropland fertilisation

Figure 6 depicts the quantity of nitrogen that can **actually** be applied to cropland areas in each major region of the world ("Space" in blue on the Figure 6) ($n_{s,c}^i$, see section 2.4.5), as well as the available organic nitrogen sources (from manure and urban areas) ("N available") from animal production. In green, it represents the quantity of **synthetic** nitrogen ($nsynth_{i,c}^{BiodivA}$, see section 2.4.5) that can be applied, which is the difference between "Space" and "N available".

Figure 6 Nitrogen application on cropland, sources and limit

It is then evident that for three major regions of the world, the quantity of synthetic nitrogen that can be applied to cropland surfaces exceeds the maximum nitrogen quantities ("Space"). This is particularly the case for North Africa and the Middle East, Europe, and also for China with a quantity of synthetic fertilizer of -2×10^9 Mg. This figure highlights especially that for certain regions of the world, the nitrogen quantities from urban areas are already higher or equal to the maximum amount of nitrogen that can be applied to crops. For example, in Europe, the nitrogen from urban areas is 1.2×10^9 Mg while the maximum nitrogen quantity for cultivated areas is set at approximately 8×10^8 Mg. Therefore, there is no space to apply synthetic nitrogen to cultivated areas.

3.3. Plant and animal production gaps

Figure 7 illustrates the biomass produced for each category of plant products as well as the demand under a "healthy" diet, with low consumption of animal products, as defined by Agrimonde Terra for 2050. The boundaries we have defined appear to be very restrictive for plant production, as our scenario is currently unable to meet the demand for any of the crop products, except for oilcrops and pulses.

In the BiodivA scenario, cereal production doesn't even reach half of the demand (3×10^{12} Mg vs. 1×10^{12} Mg) (Figure 7). This significant gap can be explained by certain formalization choices. For example, crop rotations were defined based on the organic rotation presented by Barbieri et al. (2017) (see section 2.2.7). However, this rotation leads to a 35% decrease in cereal area. Therefore, even with maximum yields, it is unlikely that the cereal demand would be met. Conversely, with this rotation,

legumes produce more biomass than the demand. Rather than applying an organic rotation, it might be considered to implement rotations more crop food-oriented rather than feed-oriented. Also, it might be possible to propose more drastic dietary changes than the "healthy" diet, which is in the high range of the EAT Lancet diets for the livestock products share.

Finally, in our scenario, nitrogen constraints are the most limiting factor for plant production, which can also explain the significant gap between production and plant demand. It seems necessary to find a way to provide more nitrogen but also to avoid these losses. For example, we only considered the effect of intercropping or the presence of semi-natural vegetation on yield. However, increasing diversity of a system necessarily modifies water and nitrogen fluxes. Although intercropping doesn't seem to have an effect on nitrogen gas emissions (Gui et al., 2024), the presence of cover crops or the integration of perennial plants (nitrogen-fixing trees) in association with the main crop seems to reduce leaching and maximize nitrogen recycling. An evaluation of these potential modifications of nitrogen fluxes and their integration into our scenario are therefore avenues to explore.

Figure 7 Plant production in BiodivA scenario and plant uses in the healthy diet scenario of Agrimonde Terra at global scale in 2050

For monogastric systems, the demand for food energy (still based on the healthy diet of Agrimonde Terra) seems to be covered by the model, or even exceeded. This can be explained by the assumptions made in the model. Indeed, pigs and poultry are mainly fed by food waste. However, we assumed that 100% of food waste energy was available, whereas a lower percentage of food losses i quantities is mentioned in the literature (Saleemdeen et al., 2017).

For ruminant systems, we made a strong assumption by assuming that all systems were efficient and homogeneous. Still, our scenario does not seem to cover the demand for food energy for meat (43% of the demand) and for dairy products (60% of the demand).

Figure 8 Food energy demand covered by BiodivA (%)

3.4. Pasture nitrogen balances

Figure 9 N inputs and outputs from pastures

The nitrogen inputs and outputs for pastures are almost balanced in the major regions of the world (N inputs = N outputs) (Figure 9). However, we notice that three regions stand out with higher nitrogen quantities per hectare (<100 kg/ha): Brazil, Latin America, and Europe. This can be explained by a higher density of cattle ruminants and therefore a higher quantity of nitrogen from

excretions in these regions (Figure 4 and 10). Indeed, only 10% of the nitrogen consumed (grass) by ruminants is converted into animal products, while the rest ends up in excretions (Figure 10).

Figure 10 Nitrogen inputs and outputs from ruminant systems

4. Summary results

The model highlights the major constraints concerning nitrogen fertilisation to produce crops needed to feed a forecast population of 9.6 billion people in 2050. As shown in Figure 5, the amount of nitrogen that can be applied to crops to respect the limits compatible with low eutrophication of natural environments is low, and only allows the existence of low-input systems. This preliminary conclusion needs to be reinforced by in-depth modelling of the fate of nitrogen once it is dispersed from farmland through watersheds and before it ends up in river mouths.

5. Implications for TC4BE, policy and stakeholders in the agri-food systems

This scenario, which presents a global agricultural and food system compatible with high levels of both agricultural and natural biodiversity, therefore seems difficult to achieve. This result means that we need to find ways of meeting this food demand. One lever that is currently being explored with Marie Ruillé's post-doc is the differential effect of field space mixing on yields of intercropped species. The literature seems to present intercropping as an effective low-input solution for increasing yields, but there is still a lack of generalisable large-scale estimates of the specific effect on cereals, which are the crop category whose demand is least satisfied in our scenario.

The redistribution of agricultural production between the world's major regions associated with this scenario seems significant. In future analyses, it will be interesting to see how the countries at the centre of this project (Kenya, Colombia and Cameroon) are affected by these production reallocations and how this changes their national strategies for their agricultural and food systems.

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